

Misleading review on vitamin C and cardiac patients by Hill et al. (2018)

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See a parallel description of flaws in another report

by Hill A, Wendt S, Stoppe C, Adhikari NKJ, Heyland DK, Benstoem C, et al. (2019)

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<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12020586>

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by Langlois PL, Adhikari NKJ, Stoppe C, Hill A, Heyland DK, et al. (2019)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19855543>

See a parallel description of flaws in another report

by Hill A, Stoppe C, et al. (2023)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19861834>

Comment on:

Hill A, Wendt S, Benstoem C, Neubauer C, Meybohm P, Langlois P, Adhikari NK, Heyland DK, Stoppe C.

Vitamin C to Improve Organ Dysfunction in Cardiac Surgery Patients-Review and Pragmatic Approach.

Nutrients. 2018;10(8):974.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30060468>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

The paper misleads the readers in several sections.

Page 4 of the PDF version of Hill et al. states: “Fowler et al observed ... a reduced 28-day mortality after the application of vitamin C in patients with sepsis and multi-organ-failure.”

This is based on Fowler’s Supplementary table 1, where he published that 62.5% of placebo participants died, but only 50.6% of high vitamin C dosage participants died.²

However, there were just 8 participants in both groups. This means that 5 of 8 participants died in the placebo group, and 4 of 8 participants died in the vitamin C group. This gives $P(2-t) = 1.0$ in the Fisher’s exact test. Thus, the very minor difference between the small study groups is explained by chance. There is no justification claim that vitamin C had a causal effect on (reduced) mortality.

Page 7 of Hill’s PDF version states: “... as demonstrated in an RCT by Dingchao et al. in the 1990s [86]. In this RCT including 85 patients...”

Dingchao et al. [86] did not report the method of allocation.³ The trial may have used alternative allocation or some other allocation method. There is no basis to state that the trial was randomized.

Furthermore, in our analysis on vitamin C and ICU stay we comment the Dingchao trial as follows:⁴

“The Dingchao trial is the oldest, carried out in China in the early 1990s. They reported that intravenous administration of 17 g/day of vitamin C for one single day reduced the length of ICU stay by 44% (95% CI 40% to 49%). On the basis of the comparison of the confidence intervals, and the heterogeneity test, the Dingchao trial is fundamentally inconsistent with all the [twelve] trials shown in Figure 3. The methods of the Dingchao trial are poorly reported; however, we do not consider that there is reasonable justification to exclude it. However, even if the study findings were valid in the context of China in the 1990s, the results cannot be generalized to the contexts examined in the more recent trials. All the more recent trials found the effect of vitamin C to be much smaller (Figure 3). Nevertheless, the Dingchao study supports the concept that vitamin C can influence ICU stay.”

Page 7 of Hill’s PDF version states: “In a systematic review [88] and in 6 different meta-analyses including 8–15 RCTs [59,60,63,89–91], vitamin C was shown to significantly reduce the occurrence of postoperative cardiac arrhythmia, mainly atrial fibrillation (AF). However, the

2 Fowler AA 3rd, et al. Phase I safety trial of intravenous ascorbic acid in patients with severe sepsis. J Transl Med. 2014;12:32.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24484547>

3 Dingchao H, Zhiduan Q, Liye H, Xiaodong F. The protective effects of high-dose ascorbic acid on myocardium against reperfusion injury during and after cardiopulmonary bypass. Thorac Cardiovasc Surg. 1994;42(5):276-8.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/7863489>
<https://zenodo.org/records/8287478>

4 Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C can shorten the length of stay in the ICU: A meta-analysis. Nutrients. 2019;11(4):708.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30934660>

results of these meta-analyses might be strongly influenced by publication bias, as discussed by Hemilä [92].”

That misleads readers. Although I pointed out in [92]⁵ that there was publication bias in one of the reviews [89], that does not mean that “*the results of [all] these meta-analyses might be strongly influenced by publication bias*”. In our own meta-analysis [91] we wrote:⁶

”we do not consider that publication bias is a likely explanation for our main findings. The evidence of the benefit of vitamin C in the non-US trials is very strong and there should be a particularly large number of unpublished non-US trials to explain the findings purely as a result of researchers publishing just the positive findings. In particular, publication bias is not a reasonable explanation for the significant difference between oral and intravenous administration.”

Page 8 of Hill's PDF version states: “*In a study by Nathens et al. in 2002, the application of vitamin C decreased risk for pneumonia and ARDS with lower alveolar inflammation in a cohort of 270 mostly trauma patients [53].”*

Nathens et al. [53]⁷ did not study “vitamin C”. They studied the combination of “alpha-tocopherol and ascorbate”. If there is benefit in a vitamin C+vitamin E group, that can be explained by vitamin E alone, or by the combination of vitamin C+vitamin E. There is no justification to state that the Nathens study tested the specific effect of “the application of vitamin C”. There is empirical evidence of interaction between vitamins C and E in humans and therefore this is not pure speculation.⁸ If the specific effects of vitamin C are studied, the only difference between the trial groups should be vitamin C.

Page 9 of Hill's PDF version states: “*2.3.3. Vitamin C's Influence on the Respiratory System in Cardiac Surgery Patients ... Reduced intubation time after cardiac surgery was shown in a meta-analysis including 3 RCTs and 575 patients ... However, the heterogeneity of the included trials was high (p = 0.74) [63].”*

5 Hemilä H. Publication bias in meta-analysis of ascorbic acid for postoperative atrial fibrillation.

Am J Health Syst Pharm. 2017;74(6):372-373.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28274978>

<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/312602>

6 Hemilä H, Suonsyrjä T. Vitamin C for preventing atrial fibrillation in high risk patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. BMC Cardiovasc Disord. 2017;17(1):49.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28143406>

7 Nathens AB, Neff MJ, Jurkovich GJ, et al. Randomized, prospective trial of antioxidant supplementation in critically ill surgical patients. Ann Surg. 2002;236(6):814-22.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12454520>

8 Hemilä H, Kaprio J. Modification of the effect of vitamin E supplementation on the mortality of male smokers by age and dietary vitamin C. Am J Epidemiol. 2009;169(8):946-53.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/19218294>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2661323>

Thus, that text claims that “*intubation time after cardiac surgery ... heterogeneity of the included trials was high (p = 0.74) [63]*”. This is based on Figure 4C in [63].⁹ The P-value in a heterogeneity test indicates how easily the heterogeneity is explained by chance. P = 0.74 indicates that it is highly likely that the observed heterogeneity is caused purely by chance. Thus, the sentence “*the heterogeneity of the included trials was high (p = 0.74)*” is incorrect and misleads readers.

Figure 4C in [63]⁹ also reports that over the three included trials I-square = 0%. I-square has a scale from 0% to 100%. Level 0% means that there is absolutely no evidence of true heterogeneity and 100% means that there is extreme evidence of true heterogeneity between the analyzed trials.¹⁰ Thus, the I-square = 0% in Figure 4C in [63] is as low as any I-square ever can be, also refuting the claim “heterogeneity of the included trials was high”.

Page 4 of Hill's PDF version shows Table 1, which gives a list of assumed positive effects of vitamin C. For example:

“*Decreases risk of pneumonia and alveolar inflammation [53]*” As pointed out above, Nathens et al. [53]⁷ did not study “vitamin C” but they studied “alpha-tocopherol and ascorbate”. Furthermore, they studied “critically ill surgical patients” and there is no justification to generalize findings with such patients to wide patient groups, or to the general population, even if the effects of vitamin C might be real on “critically ill surgical patients”. There are three controlled trials in which vitamin C alone did decrease the risk of pneumonia, but the participants were under very special conditions. Although the findings indicate biological effects of “vitamin C alone” in some conditions, the practical importance is open.^{11, 12, 13}

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- 9 Geng J, Qian J, Si W, Cheng H, Ji F, Shen Z. The clinical benefits of perioperative antioxidant vitamin therapy in patients undergoing cardiac surgery: a meta-analysis. *Interact Cardiovasc Thorac Surg*. 2017;25(6):966-974. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28645181>
- 10 Higgins JP, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003;327(7414):557-60. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12958120>
- 11 Hemilä H. Vitamin C intake and susceptibility to pneumonia. *Pediatr Infect Dis J*. 1997;16(9):836-7. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/9306475> <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/225875>
- 12 Hemilä H, Louhiala P. Vitamin C may affect lung infections. *J R Soc Med*. 2007;100(11):495-8. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18048704>
- 13 Hemilä H, Louhiala P. Vitamin C for preventing and treating pneumonia. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2013;(8):CD005532. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/23925826> <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/225862>

“Reduces rate of atrial fibrillation [59,60]” Meta-analysis [59] is seriously flawed and Hill et al. should have recognized that.¹⁴ In addition, the above statement ignores 5 RCTs in the USA that found no effect of vitamin C on atrial fibrillation.^{5,6}

Thus, there is much cherry-picking in Table 1. Studies that are inconsistent with the statements in Table 1 are ignored, and the positive findings are generalized uncritically.

There are many more problems in the review by Hill et al. but the above examples serve as an illustration.

It is particularly important to be accurate in a field that is highly controversial. The potential benefits of vitamin C for diseases other than scurvy is a controversial field. The review by Hill et al. is so inaccurate in many sections that it is not useful for readers who are interested in the potential non-scurbutic effects of vitamin C.

14 Hemilä H. Errors in a meta-analysis on vitamin C and post-operative atrial fibrillation. *Int J Surg.* 2019;64:66. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30831247>